

A human in “existential crisis” naturally seeking the humanistic-existential solution

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For a couple of weeks, I have been without a conscious thought of what I would write about for a class. I had been waking to blurred memories of my dreams. I remember the setting was usually situated at school or somehow around discussions related to life’s meanings. Of course, in my dreams, the conversations and conceptual discussion seem to flow, with wit, brilliantly. I would wake always with a felt sense (Gendlin, 1969) that the dream held some golden nugget of words given by wise mentors and professors to help me learn. I would try to repeat the phrases and describe out loud my dreams vowing to remember them better when I wake... later. Later came and I would regretfully forget, and vow, I will write it down, next time. Oh the agony of going through that hypnogogic state of rationale only to then not write down anything nor remember anything but the felt sense, over and over, again and again.

Until finally one morning, about 5:15 a.m., the somewhat meaningful dreamy words in my head became decipherable and began to make sense. With a smiling urgency I felt the words gnawing at me to write them down. Dragging myself out of bed without my glasses I managed to find our daughter’s sketch pad and a pen. I wrote,

Perspectives on “existential crisis” (in quotations)

Broke a finger nail

Broke the use of my legs

Cannot continue my subscription to cable TV

Cannot continue to buy food for my family

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At what cost to others and myself do I enslave

Kidnapped and sold as a slave

What happens What now?

What is the extent that it denies others

How do we proceed

How do we / does this help

I was relieved. I went back to bed with the paper and pen. I went straight back to sleep without writing any more. The bee hive buzzing in my head had subsided. I slept passed my alarm. I awoke and got back into my last minutes, last days of semester rush around duties with a peaceful pace and better sense of direction. I had a clearer idea of what I wanted to write about. I thought perhaps I had gone through, (experienced), what humanistic-existentialists like Rollo May, Medard Boss, and Viktor Frankl might have described as a type of crisis developed from the way I was choosing to living my life, i.e. existing (Tageson, 1982). In other words, an existential crisis. But more so, regardless if my experience was an existential “crisis” or crisis, it held for me great meaning. I knew this experience of waking frustration was not simply about the pressure involved in completing a written assignment. I had a vision of what, for my current existence in life, this dream was more authentically about. I also felt I would be able to navigate through this new awareness of myself, within this lived and living experience, with a modicum of confidence rather than my prior trepidation. I felt my angsty experience to be valid and helpful.

So what is the point? This paper is an attempt to show validity to self-described existential crisis in a variety of situations as well as similarities of how humans cope in crisis. My first inquiry in this paper is ancient and has to do with our human existence with others within the world: 1) What is meaningful to the self in crisis? The second and third question, I lay in the cradled arms of humanistic-existential psychologists (Cooper, 2003). 2) What are the meanings and understandings of an existential crisis? And 3) Is the process to navigate through the experience of an existential crisis similar for most? These questions appear to resonate in my thoughts and dreams since recently reviewing a variety of existential perspectives and certain situational and narrative examples. I am not so arrogant to think this paper to be ground breaking brilliant with wit and charm. That presence, as you read, is affixed in my sleep state. However, I am barely familiar enough with humanistic-existentialism to hopefully attempt a refreshing brief review.

Using the self-disclosed and reported personal experiences in crisis of known humanistic-existentialists like Rollo May, Medard Boss, Victor Frankl, and a few others, I have attempted to weave my own experience into theirs. Each particularly different situation and event has been broken down as it unfolded. Noted are descriptions of emotional feelings and self-interpretations the experiences have in common. The initial point is to notice if there is an universality to existential crisis and a method of humanistic-existential therapy which perhaps all beings in the

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world intuitive to get through personal crisis. The concluding point is to try to link any process of existential crisis to the application of humanistic-existential therapeutic methods designed for human growth and development.

First, a brief history of existentialist thought and the development of its philosophy. Then a short discussion on existential philosophy’s influence into the world of psychology. Following that is an overview of certain humanistic branches of existential thought and therapy specific to the existence of the human in crisis.

The shift in historical thought that seems to have broken the seal from ideas related to objective human existence came from the writings of Kierkegaard. He introduced within the realm of religion the concepts of autonomy for each person in relation to the world. In his book, *Fear and Trembling* (1983), published in 1843, Kierkegaard discussed the story of Abraham and his son Isaac, a story taken from the Old Testament Bible. To Kierkegaard, Abraham was wrought with anxiety concerning the consequences of his choice to sacrifice his son without consulting his family, however, resigned himself to his purpose and chose to follow through. Kierkegaard interpreted Abraham’s choice of faithful actions were faithful to the requests of his G-d *and* faithful to the dictates of his own conception of his true being (human understanding of existence) in the world. This very basic idea implicated faith being subjective, and subsequently, faithful actions “subject” to an individual’s true and moral self.

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After Kierkegaard came similar ideas by Nietzsche. Nietzsche too pondered self-choice in the face of crisis. He integrated this concept of autonomy and moral choice in the face of a life without a G-d. First, one example is within his book *Thus Spoke Zarathustra* (1985), published in 1891. His character known as “Übermensch” or “overman” acts as a learning guide who invites the community to a possible, more fulfilling moral life. A life most specifically suited to their given locus in life. Second, in his *The Gay Science*, published in 1882, (1974), (and in my opinion more succinctly and creatively) he engaged the concept that one’s true power comes from one becoming true to himself. This is possible only when he is present and aware of the importance of living an autonomous meaningful life-“style”.

Thus, into the 1900’s, a movement of thought and creativity unbound by the limits of living the life of a Cartesian automaton emerged. Philosophers such as Heidegger introduced us to our finite selves (alienated) in *Being in Time*, (1962) and hence to the opportunity we have in being in the moment as a more authentic self in relation with the world. Heidegger’s use of the word Dasein, translated as there-being, further came to be applied to our human existence in time and in the world. Sartre’s *Existentialism Is a Humanism* (1948) further introduced us to anti-Cartesian concepts by stating, “existence comes before essence” (Sartre, 1948 p 1). What this means is our subjective responses (i.e. responsibility) to being-in-the-world creates the worthwhile essences of life. To be in the world required action. This is inclusive and

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attributed to the notion that awareness of anguish and anxiety; a fear of no-thingness, will provide meaning, a valuation, and impetus to a life worth living. During the post WWII era, most especially within philosophical academia of East-Europe, the term existentialism for this philosophy had become, (perhaps not the most popular coined title), but widely accepted.

Post WWII there was a trans-Atlantic increase in travel across academic boundaries.

With collaboration and sharing of information between Eastern philosophers alongside the recent Western outliers of psycho-analysis, an existential philosophical seed was planted. For example, Swiss psychoanalyst Medard Boss worked with Heidegger in Germany to apply psychology to existential phenomenological concepts (Zollikon seminars, 2001). Around the year 1936 Abraham Maslow researched concepts of self-actualization under the supervision of Austro-Hungarian Gestalt therapist Max Wertheimer (Maslow & Wertheimer, Encyclopedia). Rollo May, after receiving his bachelor’s degree at Oberlin, moved to Greece and strangely found himself traveling to Vienna and studying for a bit with the Austrian therapist Alfred Adler (Ansbacher, 1990). As well, Adler worked with Maslow and Rogers. May later worked with Canadian psychologist Henri Ellenberger and two others to publish, possibly the first existential psychology book, *Existence* (1958). Many more examples like these occurred. Out of a portion of these existential seedlings stemmed the humanistic psychological human potential movement (Murphy, Horney, Houston, May) also known as the third wave of psychology. Which in turn

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sprouted, and continues to do so, a not small number of phenomenological and existential-humanistic psychologists.

Existentialism is... experiential. Each of the psychologists mentioned in this paper wrote and or spoke about personal lived experiences. One or a few experiences influenced a change in their perspective on their positioning within the life world and field of study. Their awakenings came amidst an existential quake. Some type of moment in facing reality shook the ground beneath each one, in the form of a crisis of existence, and encouraged each person to pursue solid ground. Faith came as each one moved forward. Each of the experiences occurred prior to their chosen profession and trajectory into their existential-humanistic psychological fields. The pursuit to help others, in the face of a crisis, became the purpose.

For Rollo May, the search for meaning in life moved and turned from his own experiences. Upon a bout of exhaustion, he discovered painting gave him energy. Upon meeting Adler, he pursued teaching. Working with Tillich on personal spirituality he was inspired to reach out to others. Certainly, these moments moved him to further pursue something, however still, for him, something objective in form. Until, looking in the face of death with Tuberculosis during his doctoral studies, he found subjective thought through Kierkegaard (Pitchford, 2009). He applied the idea that what he thought mattered in *his* life was what mattered in life. Giving a purpose to his anxiety came “from being unsure in life and the reality of mortality.(CITE)” He began to realize his fear and discontentedness was brought about from not being able to understand and cope with not existing.

Likewise, my thoughts within my dreams seemed out of reach. Like a precious love never to be found. Sounds a bit dramatic, but upon awakening, the sense I get from my dreams can be exactly like that, sensational. Sometimes my dreams are fantasy and fun moments. I am Ok with not pursuing in my waking life details I do not remember. But the dreams I mentioned prior were saddening. It was like a goal attainable for others that will, for me, never come to pass. I went along my days, from time to time, noticing my limits- with a magnifier. Occasionally, I sought approval and validation, (not, by the way, my forte), to then find myself absconded away and feeling a bit ridiculous. Paradoxically, for May, his awareness to a meaningless life was given meaning and the avenue to personal growth. Mixing an illness like tuberculosis with full spoons of nothingness and intention seemed the correct medicinal cocktail for May to get better. He enhanced his notions of anxiety to include experiences near death along with everyday experiences in life. The normal and the neurotic anxiety was to be understood as levels of coping and awareness, not the extremity of the occurring crisis (May, 1996).

For Medard Boss, the crisis came about from his experiences in academics and working as an analyst. Boss’ life on the surface looked as though he were born and groomed to fly the Freudian flag of psychoanalysis. He grew up in Zurich, studied there and was analyzed by Freud (Boeree, 1998). However, along his academic and therapeutic path were the subtle influences of non-traditional psychoanalysts such as Karen Horney. Horney questioned certain aspects related to Freudian therapy. She believed the Freudian view of anxiety lacked the inclusion of humans’ social and cultural life experience, as it is lived, i.e. as we exist in the social world (Encyclopedia Britannica) Her ideas, to Freudians, often defiled the schools of psychoanalysis, but for others, she opened doors to new schools of possibilities of self-evaluation and growth (Horney, 2013).

After ten years of workshops with Carl Jung, another Freudian dissident, Boss was getting closer to what made sense in his pursuit of psychological therapy methods. He remained, (albeit sometimes confused but), open to these subliminal clues that were diverting him away from traditional psychoanalysis. The answers for him came from his introduction to Heidegger’s work via the existential analyst, Ludwig Binswanger (Moss, 1978).

It was at this time Boss met Heidegger. Boss stated, “... about this time I met Heidegger and saw that Heidegger was much more the way I am built (Craig, 1988)”. At this point in his life, it seems the psychology of humans-being came into focus. In his becoming a daseinanalyst he was able to see the experience of life, as it lives in the world for himself, existentially, and most especially, in a way he had not before. He said, “I owed it to my patients to have a sounder foundation of my understanding in order to help them, really. So, it was my patients who forced me to go beyond what our psychology had taught (Craig, 1988)”. Ultimately it was Boss experiencing the human in-experience that helped him to recognize his prior dilemma; in the way he was “built” to fit. For me in the dream experience, I had a difficult time forming myself within the world. My daily grind became a blind hopefulness in monotony. I knew I was on the right path. But also knew I had to continue looking for the turn. I thought I was missing something, until the missing something appeared. Unlike Boss, I flip-flopped a bit trying to see if I could figure out and remember the details in my dreams. I can see now, I was forcing a blank screen to image itself. It was part of a process in fruitlessness.

Boss discussed in his book *Existential Foundations of Medicine and Psychology* (Boss, 1977) the basics of existential anxiety being a feeling of existence somehow being in danger. Further, he expressed the clue to processing out of this type of Dasein (being-there) is the

recognition of deeper feelings that may attribute to the anxious state of being. A self-evaluation of what possibly is arousing this fear is noted by him to be helpful. Is the person feeling passionate, sad, overjoyed? In other words, he developed a therapeutic manner for humans to take a critical view of their selves (Boss, 1977). I believe his experience influenced and manifested his therapeutic methods. As he was able to recognize his personal fit-ness and openness with the help of Heidegger, Boss was more able to invite others to being open to a personal meaningful existence. I can admit part of the process, as I meandered through my dream-crisis, was a beginning realization there may be some intention to my struggle. I had a sense of determination. I had a driving sense that understanding the crisis would help me to survive it (Adams, 2016).

Which brings into focus Victor Frankl’s experiences and subsequent notions of the existential vacuum (Frankl, 1969) and the tragic triad (Frankl, 1990). These notions are expounded in these readings further, but first a brief span of Frankl’s life. Pertinent to this essay, a synopsis of prior experiences, reported by Frankl, to have contributed to the conceptualization of his existential philosophy embedded with logotherapy.

Frankl was born in Austria, 1905 (For more information, see “Frankl Biography” in the bibliography). An avid scholar philosopher from early in his education; in high school he began a correspondence with Freud. At 19 years old he published his first psychology article in the *International Journal of Psychoanalysis* (1924) and continued his education influenced by perspectives of Adler. He then migrates over to study the psychosomatic medicinal views of Allers and Schwarz (Corbett, 2016). At what seems to be a directed pace, while practicing therapy, Frankl wrote the article *Philosophy and Psychotherapy: On the Foundation of an*

Existential Analysis. This article is where the method name “existential analysis” is known to have been coined (Frankl Biography). This new footing of understanding of how to apply existential being and healing to a type of therapy was the impetus to beginning his first book in 1941, *The Doctor and the Soul* (1986), originally published in 1946. The timing when he started that book could not have been more appropriate for supplying him with a strong faith there was a soul to psychology. He moved forward with the curiosity, resilience and empathy he would need to use in the following few years. It was in the next year he and his family were arrested and forced to moved to a Jewish ghetto. In 1944, he was taken first to Auschwitz and later moved to two other Dachau subsidiary concentration camps.

As he described his time in the concentration camps (Frankl, 1992), Frankl broke down the phases that he believed can lead any human faced with the fear of non-existence into and out of a state of anxiety. The temporal phases begin with thoughts of fear, suicide, death, then to apathy, moments of indignation and a cultural hibernation (p 45). During this process an existential meaningfulness develops from a sense of hope within the “inner life” (p 50). This hope is glorified nostalgia which brings about a calm contemplation of life’s purpose. He wrote,

Another time we were at work in a trench. The dawn was grey around us; grey was the sky above; grey the snow in the pale light of dawn; grey the rags in which my fellow prisoners were clad, and grey their faces. I was again conversing silently with my wife, or perhaps I was struggling to find the *reason* for my sufferings, my slow dying. In a last violent protest against the hopelessness of imminent death, I sensed my spirit piercing through the enveloping gloom. I felt it transcend that hopeless, meaningless, world, and from somewhere I heard a victorious “Yes” in answer to my question of the existence of an ultimate purpose. At that moment a light was lit in a distant farmhouse, which stood on the horizon as if painted there, in the midst of the miserable grey of the dawning morning... (1992 p 51).

To me, Frankl’s experiences, as he relays them, epitomize the universality equated with existential crisis. His specific examples are extreme, for some, but what is similar is the deeper meaning it holds for all humans in the world. As a WWII concentration camp survivor, from a surface level, his experience at first may seem, to the outsider, to induce a sense of guilt. Although if we understand guilt being, like anxiety, a natural sense of self, not to be awakened by a scenario but more by a feeling, then a new recognition emerges. Guilt is one point on Frankl’s tragic triad which also includes suffering and death. Logotherapy seeks to make sense of the suffering and the reality of dying. All three are proposed to influence crisis occurrence and as well infuse an understanding for the reason and what purpose or value the crisis offers (Frankl, 1985). In the preface to Frankl’s book, *Man’s Search for Meaning* (1992), Allport succinctly stated, “...the central theme of existentialism. To live is to suffer, to survive is to find meaning in the suffering.” (1992, p 10).

In this book (1992), Frankl enhances the existentialist concepts of choice and responsibility by introducing logotherapy to existential humanistic psychology. This book is considered an autobiographical account of his experiences and his observations of others in anxiety. Additionally, his work may be considered as well, like this paper, an autoethnography (Esping, 2013). This being an existential self-narrative to further expression and awareness of being and the value of existence, in, within, and out of crisis (Esping, 2010).

Much like May and Boss, he applied his deeper understanding of himself, as he experienced life, to move beyond the constraints that bound psychoanalysis. He viewed Freud’s will to pleasure and Adler’s will to power as being at the surface. Their ideas covering what, as he came to believe, stemmed from the human’s natural will to meaning. In other words, the

emptiness in the vacuum appears empty because a purpose in being, the root of our existence from which our crisis may develop, is left unrecognized (Frankl, 1992 & 1990). To Frankl, “man’s search for meaning is the primary motivation for his life” (Frankl, 1992 p 105).

Applicable to my dream scenario, it is obvious that I was searching for more details in the dreams. I have had plenty of hazy dreams, never to recall. But hardly one of them kept my interest to investigate such as these. So, to understand this on a deeper level as an existential crisis, I was motivated to understand what its significance is to my own personal search for meaning in life.

As we know, many of the WWII Nazi holocaust victims did not survive the war to fulfill a further purpose in life. One cannot be led astray to think those without a purpose were those who do not survive. That is a detour this paper will not turn. We discuss the experience of humanistic-existential psychological trailblazers as fallible humans rather than the shoulders of giants we rest upon. The retrospect is clear this paper’s needs to be addressed are on being human, via their experiences. In context, the important factor is acknowledging experientially there is a purpose of existence, even when the path is one less thought of as appropriate to travel.

The life of humanistic-existential psychologist R.D. Laing seemed to have been braided with a journey filled with victories and defeat, roads less traveled and often waters too deep to swim. What is consistent along his life was his pursuit in replacing the Cartesian human object with the “self-acting agent” (Laing, 1960, p 22). To expose and differentiate the face from the vase (Laing, 1960); the person who is free to be in relation with his/her world. For his own personal experience, Laing was an only child whose early life was riddled with loneliness and confusion. Laing often spoke about his family relationships as being tethered by dysfunction.

His father was often away working. When home, his father was heavily drinking alcohol. His father and grandfather displayed heated fights in the den. Laing told a story he remembers as the only time his father gifted a birthday present to his mother; an elegantly wrapped box, within a box which held his father’s toenail clippings (Brockway, 1973). However, Laing also spoke of sentimental moments with his father he cherished such as learning to play piano with him. Laing shared a room with his mother until puberty. His relationship with her was volatile too. She often destroyed his most special toys and was strict with him to excel in academics (Burston, 1998, and Cohen, 2016).

These experiences would help to explain a portion of his existential journey being led by his most well-known attribute of being a voraciously curious empath with a desire (sometimes obsessive drive) to show other psychologists the same path towards empathy. His calling became clearer upon his introduction to methods of traditional psychiatry practiced in institutions. From his first days at hospital, like Frankl, he recognized the lack of soul in therapeutic psychology. He used his voice and actions to reflect a soul; the subjective face rather than the objective vase to mainstream psychology. His goal was validating the lived experience of patients diagnosed with schizophrenia; patients whose madness was deemed extreme and untreatable. I would infer, his insight concerning psychosis, being a participatory way of coping with crisis, came partly from his own life experiences and observations of his parents’ peculiar behaviors.

A hero to many, he is known to have been proud of his achievements and often sought competitively to stay atop a pedestal. He developed an impish manner in social settings and an easy-going attitude which lent him a certain amount of leeway and attention in academic circles.

However, among other academics who did not approve to avail this manner, he came across as arrogant and rude. On certain occasions he did behave in manners one might understand as reactive from a lack of coping. This was most prevalent in the late 1970’s into the start of the 1980’s as his second marriage came to an end (Burston, 1996). For example, he was often inebriated at psychology conferences and TV appearances (Byrne, 2012 and Burston, 1998). As well his adult life as a father of ten from four different mothers, a few of his children agree his behavior as a father was often abusive and dysfunctional (Cohen, 2016 and Laing, A, 2006). But, to the suffering client, his authentic regard and care showed little boundaries. Not a perfect fit, but a fitting existential statement, in this context, is his belief, “We live on the hope that authentic true meeting between humans can occur” (Laing, 1965). Perhaps it is telling that his crisis came alongside a new (i.e. neo) tangled existential showcase of academic rebels whose stardom sprouted up and over Laing’s popular antics in the mid 1980’s. There was a public expression of disdain in academia for Laing’s breakdown (Burston, 1998). Sadly, there seems to have been no psychologists who claim they reached out to help Laing “break-through” (Laing, 1990 p 110).

To every existential crisis the availability of hope resides within the authenticity of our given syncretic sociality. I remember a portion of my dream had me speechlessly listening to a fellow student I felt to be ungratefully whining. That morning I awoke with an indignation more righteously arrogant than hopeful and helpful. I could not remember much of my dream except a lingering sense of entitlement to pity my classmate. Digging deeper into my personal crisis of existence, as a self-professed non-dualist, I began to expose my barnacled underbelly, bumpy of

arrogant judgmental dualism. Oh my and ouch! I realized, I had kept waking and yearning not simply to know more but also to understand more than others.

Somehow this seems the top of the roller coaster for me. I begin to see myself as May saw himself; grateful. I see myself perhaps as Boss sees me; to be directed by the mentors that help me along a path, like Laing’s, one I have never mapped. I am only thirteen pages into a paper when I am led to the local grocery store. I walk the aisles aimlessly but knowing it’s where I need to be. I run into a former professor who met R.D. Laing. It is as if every time I see her, she has a smile and a helpful nudge of enthusiasm for me. Not just for me, I know this because I watch other faces smile as she turns heads. Her existence does not appear to be riddled with objects in her path. She shops with a small cart. Some cereal, a little bag of cold cuts, two loaves of bread. She tells me stories and takes my address to mail me a book I may find interesting. This person is one who I respect so dearly for her humanness and her great humility. I find this event delightfully refreshing given my task ahead. I left the store fortified with a little more “perceptual faith” (Merleau-Ponty, 1968 p 103) that more would be revealed.

And so it did. I was reminded of Cooper (2003) noting Van Deurzen’s criticized Laing for compartmentalizing anxiety. Her point being that ontological insecurity is within us all. She wrote, “No matter how securely a person is established in the world, some events will shake the foundations of that security and transform the appearance of existence (Van Deurzen, 2007, p 202)”. Perhaps a mentor goes through crisis at the grocery store. Two loaves of bread? She and her husband have a lot of bread to eat. Was it a sale? Is she buying for someone else? Such very small mundane daily tasks but truly, as Cooper mentioned this in his book, *Existential Theories* (2003) “the dread of nothingness and sense of not-at-home-ness at the heart of the human

condition, and this as existential philosophers have argued, is an experience that all human beings face” (p 104). This is the crux of the answer to one of this paper’s inquiry. Anxiety and the process to potential enlightenment is not solely for the one with psychosis, nor the victims of atrocity. It is manifested in our lives, fashioned as reminders, great and small, of our existence as it presents itself to us.

The list of experiences from our existential-humanistic psychologists do crack open the door to the universality of how angst is perceived and personified. But lest we forget, as well do their clients and characters inform us. J.H. van den Berg (1972) exposed us to his changing bottle of wine. But further, it is our intersubjective presence, invited by his client to view the buildings looming above, where we see the world as it could be lived. Merleau-Ponty connects our body schema with meaning by understanding the real existence of pain as it pierces the “phantom limb” (2013, p 101). It is Tarrou’s recognition with Dr. Rieux that Camus implored us to understand we are all in the plague, but we don’t all have to be victims of the plague (Camus, 1967). Absurdity aside, the father and son in McCarthy’s *The Road* (2006) shows us there is meaning in the absurdity of dying in a post-apocalyptic life-world.

In coming to conclusion, there is a consoling fervor in the air. Our existential journey is not mapped alone nor, can it be traveled solo. It requires a relationship with the world. My anxiety, dynamic and plastic, is in relation with the world. The existential crisis takes form and in healing is broken down. For “break-through” our anxiety is attached to a version of faith in a process focused in a continuation to being-active-in-the-world. The faith is obscure in the meaninglessness. But for me, when I continued to seek with openness in my waking and sleep states, I found meaning creep into my maudlin position. I was able to re-orient my search from

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remembering *scenes* in the dreams in relation with being awakened, to a more natural search for understanding the *feelings* emergent to me by the dream.

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